

**SUBMERGED ARC WELDING OF BUTT JOINTS OF GRADE A SHIPBUILDING STEEL SHEETS
ON ONE SIDE IMMEDIATELY AFTER PLASMA CUTTING**

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ABSTRACT

This study is dedicated to developing approaches for applying submerged arc welding to extended sheet shipbuilding structures (such as panels and beams) made of low-carbon steel immediately after plasma cutting, without additional edge preparation. The selected submerged arc welding parameters allow for achieving satisfactory weld quality when welding edges produced by plasma cutting without further processing. A positive effect was observed in all specimens. It has been established that without securing the welding head to the deforming surface of the welded components, the electrode overhang decreases, and welding mode parameters change up to arc interruption. Specialized equipment is required to correct such deflection, and the presence of weld reinforcement complicates the straightening operation. Furthermore, conventional single-sided, single-pass submerged arc welding on ceramic forming backing strips, despite the beneficial influence of the substantial heat capacity of the welding flux, leads to the formation of hardened microstructures in the weld metal and reduces its ductility due to significant cooling rates and the rapid progression of phase transformations.

Keywords: single-sided single-pass submerged arc welding, shipbuilding steel grade A, edge welding after plasma cutting, weld bead shaping, microstructure, pore minimization.

Submerged arc welding, as the primary method for fabricating panels and beams in shipbuilding, has been utilized since the early twentieth century [1]. Despite considerable research [2–4] aimed at improving the efficiency of submerged arc welding in shipbuilding practice, this technology has not experienced significant changes. The primary challenge in its application is the welding distortions occurring during the fabrication of large-scale components, which adversely affect both sectional and slipway assembly procedures, as well as the vessel's aesthetic quality. Submerged arc welding of hull structures in the vertical position is predominantly performed in a double-sided configuration (for butt joints of small thicknesses, type C7 is applied, while for thicknesses of 14 mm, type C21 is used in accordance with ISO 9692-1 and ISO 15792). The employment of such joints is justified solely from the perspective of tempering the initial pass with the subsequent one and partially reducing distortion levels, rather than fully eliminating them. Simultaneously, a double-sided weld requires operations such as structural restraint release, edge bending of the sheet, cleaning of the reverse side, and additional fastening, which are performed along the sheet perimeter rather than within the heat-affected zone. The ability of the weldable structures and fixtures to accumulate heat under

constant welding parameters leads to increased penetration depth and uneven fusion along the weld length. The effect of energy balance shifting towards melting of the welding wire with increased welding current, necessitating bead overlap, causes an increase in weld width and reinforcement height, but decreases penetration depth [5] and increases the likelihood of lack of fusion.

Studies [6–8] on mathematical modeling of the submerged arc welding process are documented; however, the multivariate nature and complexity of factors affecting the characteristics of submerged arc welding—including the thermophysical properties of the flux, welding wire, and base metal; structural differences in the deposited metal between the first and second passes; the considerable length of welds; and environmental conditions such as drafts in workshops—diminish the effectiveness of such modeling. In submerged arc welding modeling, the possibility of utilizing blanks obtained directly by plasma cutting without any mechanical processing is generally not considered. From the standpoint of enhancing the productivity of ship structure fabrication and reducing their manufacturing cost, this aspect is of critical importance.

The process of single-pass, one-sided automatic submerged arc welding using forming devices (ceramic, copper, and flux backing, copper runners) is also

preferable and economically advantageous; however, increasing the power of the heat source elevates the volume of molten metal in the weld pool and, accordingly, increases the volume of solidifying metal, thereby augmenting the degree of deformation. This phenomenon is particularly pronounced in extended joints.

Patent [9] describes an arc welding method that significantly reduces internal stresses and deformations in extended single-pass, single-sided welded joints. The concept involves suppressing the sequential polymorphic phase transformations in the weld metal that contribute to the accumulation of internal stresses, followed by post-weld tempering of the entire joint to guarantee the formation of a homogeneous ferrite-pearlite microstructure within the heat-affected zone (HAZ).

Despite recent research efforts (e.g., studies [10, 11]), the predominant approach to welding steel components cut by plasma methods remains mechanical edge preparation. This approach necessitates the implementation of a corresponding technological operation.

To reduce the cost and duration of preparing the edges of steel components for subsequent submerged arc welding, it is advisable to develop welding approaches that enable the formation of high-quality joints with minimal internal porosity and acceptable mechanical properties.

The objective of this study is to develop methodologies for applying the submerged arc welding technique to extended sheet shipbuilding structures (such as panels, beams, etc.) composed of low-carbon steel immediately following plasma cutting, without additional edge preparation.

Figure 1 depicts the external appearance of the assembled joint prepared for welding. Welded specimens (1) of grade A sheet steel measuring 100×430×5 mm were assembled according to node C4 without a gap (ISO 9692-1 and ISO 15792), on technological bars (100×40×5 mm), secured by two tack welds (10–15 mm), with placement of flat ceramic pads PZ 1500/72 (2) and ceramic electric heaters KEN B-60-21-5 sized 525×105 at the root of the assembly (3).

Fig. 1. Sample assembled for welding.

Welding of the samples was performed on the automatic ADF-1250 machine using Sv-08A wire, Ø4 mm, with AN-348A flux, and the VDU-1250 unit. Heat treatment was conducted using a 70 kW power unit,

model RT70-6. The feedback sensor was a type XA thermocouple (chromel–alumel). Thermal insulation material Supersil, 10 mm thick. Welding and heat treatment modes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Welding and heat treatment modes.					
Sample number	Current I, A	Arc voltage U, V	Welding speed V, cm/min	Preheating temperature, °C	Cooling rate, °C/h
1	250	24	21	400	150
2	200	24	50	600	150
3	280	24	30	400	150
4	300	24	25	450	150
5	325	24	25	450	150
6	350	24	23	450	150

To ensure complete thermal insulation of the sample and eliminate the need to mount the tractor on the workpiece, a test rig was developed (Fig. 2) featuring

two independent platforms: a welding table and a tracker for the welding tractor.

Fig. 2. Experimental test rig.

Welding was performed without the use of fastening or clamping devices securing the sample. The assembled welding sample was placed on the table over a layer of thermal insulation material. Each plate was covered with a strip of thermal insulation, leaving a gap of 35–40 mm between the strips to allow for welding. During heating, it was also covered with a strip of thermal insulation material.

Upon reaching the programmed heating temperature, the upper layer of insulation was removed, welding was performed, and without flux removal, the sample was covered with thermal insulation, followed by programmed cooling to 150°C. The geometric parameters of the welds were measured using a metal ruler and calipers. The longitudinal deflection of the welded specimen was measured with a feeler gauge placed between the plate and an applied metal ruler.

Static tensile tests were performed using a universal servo-hydraulic testing machine, MTS 318.25 (USA, Material Test System), on type XII specimens according to GOST 6996-66. Hardness was measured

using an HR-150A hardness tester on the HRA scale on both the face and root surfaces of the welded joint with 1 mm measurement intervals from the weld center toward the base metal. Microhardness measurements across the weld cross-section were conducted on polished specimens using a Shimadzu HMV-2 series microhardness tester.

The preparation of templates cut from the welds for microstructural investigations was performed on a DeltaAbrasiMet bench abrasive machine and an EcoMet 250 Pro grinding and polishing system. Sample etching was carried out in a 5% alcoholic nitric acid solution. Structural analysis and internal defect detection were carried out using MIM-8 microscopes (magnifications 100 to 1350×) and NEOPHOT-32 microscopes (magnifications 25 to 1500×).

The application of Mode 1 (Table 1) resulted in burn-through defects (Table 2). The cause of this defect is the detachment of the ceramic backing from the sample surface, caused by excessive welding wire feed at low welding speed.

Table 2.

Appearance and dimensions of the face and root sides of the weld.

Sample		Reinforcement height, mm	Reinforcement width, mm	Longitudinal deflection, mm	Weld appearance
Number	Side				
1	Face	-4,0	17,4	10	
	Root	4,0	20,2		
2	Face	1,4	10,4	1	
	Root	0	0		
3	Face	1,3	18,3	2,5	

	Root	1,6	7,5			
4	Face	0,8	19,8	3,5		
	Root	1,4	10,6			
5	Face	1,3	23,0	3,5		
	Root	1,4	11,6			
6	Face	1,0	24,6	3		
	Root	1,8	16,4			

The increase in welding speed and the decrease in welding current in mode 2 resulted in the absence of root reinforcement formation. In sample 3, partial filling of the backing form by the root reinforcement was achieved, whereas in samples 4, 5, and 6, the weld root metal followed the contours of the ceramic backings along the entire length. The geometric parameters of the welds in welded joints produced under modes 4 and 5 correspond to joint type C4 according to ISO 9692-1 and ISO 15792, with a maximum deflection of 3.5 mm. The greatest deflection value was observed in the first specimen—10 mm.

Thermograms of all specimens are presented in Fig. 3, which demonstrates that following uniform pro-

grammed heating and welding under a thermal insulation layer at the thermocouple locations, an additional temperature increase up to 600°C occurred, substantiating that the polymorphic transformation temperature was reached in the heat-affected zone. It is also notable that in Mode 2 (preheating to 600°C), no significant temperature increase occurs during welding, indicating the impracticality of such thermal saturation, as the temperature rise after welding caused by the arc action in other modes results in self-tempering of the entire deposited metal volume and the heat-affected zone of the welded joints from the polymorphic transformation temperature, without additional heating.

Fig. 3. Thermograms of samples (vertical axis – temperature; horizontal axis – time).

Mechanical properties and microstructure tests were performed on samples with fully formed welds: 4,

5, and 6. Results of static tensile tests are presented in Table 3.

Results of static tensile testing.

Sample numbers	Tensile strength σ_B , MPa	Yield strength σ_r , MPa	Proportional limit $\sigma_{0.2}$, MPa	Relative elongation δ , %	Young's modulus, MPa
4.1	660	500	128	43	31685
4.2	548	415	89	42	25480
4.3	552	470	46	41	13697
5.1	533	390	40	42	5782
5.2	530	390	44	42	15008
5.3	527	395	36	43	12924
6.1	522	380	49	42	6809
6.2	533	390	55	47	19741
6.3	523	380	38	41	15315
Not less than					
GOST 5521-93	400-490	315	-	22	-

All specimens fractured in the base metal, and their mechanical properties comply with the requirements of ISO 630-6 for Grade A hot-rolled steel sheets. Meanwhile, the values of σ_B , σ_r , and $\sigma_{0.2}$ for specimen 4 are higher than those of specimens 5 and 6. The relative elongation values of the specimens are practically identical and exceed the base metal requirements by a factor of two.

The conducted experiments indicate that isothermal tempering positively influences not only the mechanical properties of the welded joint but also the base metal.

The microstructure of the investigated samples (Table 4, Fig. 4) is characterized by four zones: weld metal (I), recrystallization zone (II), overheating zone (III), and base metal (IV).

In the deposited metal, the weld microstructure exhibits a ferrite-pearlite structure with globular grains

lacking preferred orientation. The grain size is four times larger than that of the base metal. At the fusion line, the grain size remains unchanged, but the grains are oriented from the fusion line towards the weld center.

The recrystallization zone in samples 4, 5, and 6 exhibits an identical structure. The grain size from the fusion line towards the base metal is identical to that from the fusion line towards the weld center. This zone is characterized by a random arrangement of grains. Areas of stringer structure corresponding to the rolled material are observed at the center. This zone exhibits a gradual transition to a finer structure of the third zone.

The base metal is characterized by a fine-grained laminar structure. Sample 6 demonstrated the greatest extent of the heat-affected zone (Table 5); the smallest HAZ length on the face side was observed in sample 4, while on the reverse side of the weld, it was sample 5.

Table 4.

Microstructure of the weld joint zones, $\times 400$.

Region	Sample No.		
	4	5	6
Weld metal (I)			
Fusion line			

Re-crystallization zone (II)			
Over-heated zone (III)			
Base metal (IV)			

Fig. 4. Microstructure of welds: a) – sample No. 4; b) – sample No. 5; c) – sample No. 6.

Dimensions of heat-affected zones.

Sample number	HAZ dimension on the weld face side, mm	HAZ dimension on the weld root side, mm	Recrystallization zone area, mm ²	Transition zone area, mm ²	Total HAZ area, mm ²
4	3,7	9,4	26,4	20	46,4
5	3,9	8,2	26,5	15	41,5
6	5,2	10	32,2	22	54,2

The highest heat-affected zone areas were observed in sample 6, and the lowest in sample 5, due to an increase in welding current. Therefore, the welded joint produced under mode 5 is the most optimal.

The hardness profiles across the surfaces of the examined samples (Fig. 5) revealed a minimum hardness

value of 47 HRA in the outer reinforcement regions of samples 4 and 5, corresponding to the hardness values specified for Grade A steel sheet in the as-delivered state (42 HRA).

Fig. 5. Graphs of hardness distribution across the surfaces of the face and reverse sides of the weld (1 – hardness of the outer weld surface; 2 – hardness at the weld root): a) sample No. 4; b) sample No. 5; c) sample No. 6.

In the deposited metal and heat-affected zone (HAZ), on both the face and reverse sides of the weld, the average hardness values of the samples are identical. When comparing the hardness of the samples, the values are approximately equal. The hardness value exhibits a uniform distribution from the center of the weld

to the base metal. Graphs of microhardness distribution across the cross-section are presented in Figure 6. Samples 4, 5, and 6 demonstrate uniform microhardness distribution in the heat-affected zone.

Fig. 6. Graphs of microhardness distribution across the weld cross-section (1 – measured hardness; 2 – linear hardness): a) Sample No. 4; b) Sample No. 5; c) Sample No. 6.

The boundary complexity was evaluated by fractal dimension, determined using Image-Pro Plus software. Figure 7 presents the measurement results and calculated quantitative indicators of the perimeter and area of microstructural features.

The histograms of the distribution indicate that the first sample exhibits the highest values of average area and fractal dimension, reflecting more developed grain boundary interfaces. This observation corresponds to superior strength characteristics of the welded joint,

consistent with the distinctly dendritic structure of the sample.

In samples 4, 5, and 6, from the weld metal zone to the recrystallization zone, an increase in fractal dimension is observed, followed by a decrease toward the base metal zone; this is attributed to the well-developed boundaries in the recrystallization zone, corresponding to higher hardness values in this region.

Fig. 7. Histograms of distribution (I – weld metal zone; II – fusion line; III – recrystallization zone; IV – heat-affected zone; V – base metal): a) mean object area; b) fractal dimension.

No internal defects were detected during microstructural analysis.

Conclusion.

The selected submerged arc welding parameters allow for achieving satisfactory weld quality when welding edges produced by plasma cutting without further processing. A positive effect was observed in all specimens. The dimensions of the welded and tested

samples are limited in size, which enables evaluation of the weld quality formed when welding edges immediately after plasma cutting and only allows indirect assessment of the success of welding extended joints without deformation. The final point requires further investigation. Nevertheless, welding without preheating or controlled volumetric cooling, and without clamping the welded parts to the fixture, necessitates higher welding current values and induces longitudinal

deformations with deflections up to 50 mm over a weld length of 430 mm. When the welding head is not fixed to the deforming surface of the welded parts, electrode extension decreases and welding mode parameters change, potentially leading to arc interruption. Specialized equipment is required to correct such deflection, and the presence of weld reinforcement complicates the straightening operation. Furthermore, conventional single-sided, single-pass submerged arc welding on ceramic forming backing strips, despite the beneficial influence of the substantial heat capacity of the welding flux, leads to the formation of hardened microstructures in the weld metal and reduces its ductility due to significant cooling rates and the rapid progression of phase transformations.

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